

SCIENTIFIC TEXT AS A SOURCE OF ENRICHMENT OF PROFESSIONAL SPEECH

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Abstract: The article reveals the theoretical and methodological foundations of studying a scientific text at a university. The article also discusses the issues of definitions of the concepts of "text" and "scientific text", as well as the structure of scientific texts, their features, language tools that are used in scientific works.

Keywords: text, scientific style, communicative competence, self-development, self-expression, linguistics.

Introduction

The state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan focuses on the progress of society, the training of highly qualified personnel, modern specialists. The President of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, argues that it is necessary to focus on the education of young people, while "strengthening the ideological immunity of student youth, educating them with high moral and human dignity." He noted that "we should talk more with young people, listen to their opinions, know what they care about, and provide practical assistance in solving problems," which is a priority task of the country's educational system.

Young people, in particular, students, under the influence of internal motives and needs, build a system of their educational goals as part of their inner world. In this regard, it becomes relevant to form and develop a way of thinking among students that contributes to the acquisition and production of new knowledge, arming them with skills of self-development and self-expression, since the processes of socialization of the individual become continuous, continuing throughout life. In connection with the above, the development of students' general academic skills, i.e. mechanisms of acquisition, organization and application of knowledge acquired at the university.

Currently, elements of a new educational system, fundamentally different in its structure and content, are really being manifested and implemented, a transition is being made from a reproductive model of education that works for the reproduction and stability of existing social relations to a productive, humanistic, culturally oriented system.

University teachers have long recognized the need to use new methods and technologies in the process of studying the discipline "Russian language" and all disciplines of the curriculum.

Teaching students the Russian language on the basis of the State Standard program, the goal is to form future specialists' communicative competence - the ability to solve real communicative tasks by linguistic means in specific speech situations of the scientific sphere, the formation of intercultural and communicative competence of students in the process of education, as well as the acquisition of professional vocabulary (terms) in the process of studying various disciplines. Based on the above, it is clear that in the country's

universities it is necessary to prepare students for the future profession, to increase the literacy of young students in the field of science by referring to dictionaries of a terminological nature.

The concept of "text" cannot be defined only linguistically. The text is, first of all, a communicative concept focused on identifying the specifics of a certain type of activity. In other words, the text as a set of some signs, as a process and product of the sign activity of the communicator and the recipient, is in the context of a certain realization of some communicative text.

The text appears to us not as an implementation of a message in any one language, but as a complex device storing diverse codes that can transform the messages received and generate new ones. The text is an information generator with the features of an intellectual personality. In this regard, the perception of the relationship between the consumer and the text is changing. Instead of the formula: "the consumer decrypts the text" — a more accurate one is possible: "the consumer communicates with the text". He comes into contact with him. The process of deciphering the text becomes extremely complicated, loses its one-time and final character, approaching the familiar acts of semiotic communication of a person with another autonomous personality.

The term "text" comes from the Latin "textus", which means fabric, plexus, connection. It can be defined as a sequence of speech units united by semantic and grammatical connection: utterances, super-phrasal units (prose stanzas), fragments, sections, etc..

Traditionally, the concept of "text" was attributed only to works of written speech and was defined as a graphic representation of a "piece" of reality. There are other definitions of the concept of "text". Here are some of them. "Any sequence of sentences organized in time or space in a way that suggests a whole will be considered a text."

The development of a new branch of linguistics – the linguistics of text – required determining the status of the unit that became the object of our study, in relation to the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language. The question of the relation of the text to language and speech is still debatable, some scientists attribute the text to the language system and recognize its symbolic nature. "Probably, this is true only for texts of a "rigid" structure."

In modern approaches to the concept of text, there is a different interpretation and definition of it. Being a work of the "speech-making process", possessing "completeness", objectified "in the form of a written document", literarily processed "in accordance with the type of this document", the text consists of "a title (title) and a number of special units (super-phrasal units) united by different types of lexical, grammatical, logical, stylistic connection", has "a certain purposefulness and pragmatic attitude".

A text is a message existing in the form of such a sequence of signs that has formal coherence, meaningful integrity and a formal semantic structure arising on the basis of their interaction.

The text is understood as a hierarchically constructed sense formation implemented in speech and structured in structural and intonational terms.

The study of the scientific style of speech at the university has both theoretical and practical significance. Russian Theoretical knowledge about the functional aspect of the language, therefore, about the Russian language as a whole, serves as a foundation for practical work in Russian language classes at the university, increases the linguistic and

stylistic culture of students, which is an essential part of their general culture, in particular, the culture of speech. In this regard, we believe that it is important for the student: 1) initial familiarization with the scientific style of speech, the basic concepts, principles of the speech organization of styles, the laws of the functioning of linguistic means in scientific speech; 2) the development of stylistic flair, skills and abilities to evaluate and correctly use linguistic means in speech acts in accordance with the specific content of the utterance, the goals set by the speaker (writer), the situation and the sphere of communication.

The text as a fact of a speech act is systematic. A text is a kind of complete message with its content, organized according to an abstract model of one of the forms of messages existing in the literary language (functional style, its varieties and genres). The scientific text and all its categories receive their specific forms of implementation. When it comes to corruption in education, a thousand unfortunately continue to increase as much as it is fought against it.

The ability to express your thoughts clearly and clearly, to speak competently, the ability not only to attract attention with your speech is a kind of characteristic of professional suitability for people of various professions, especially for future specialists: lawyers, engineers, university teachers, radio and television workers, managers, including mechanics, builders, power engineers.

Conclusion

So, high-quality didactic material is of great importance for the development of students' speech, which can be a scientific text that students encounter in the classroom, both Russian and other special disciplines, as well as speech situations that take place in the practice of teaching students and described in scientific works (textbooks, teaching aids). The teacher needs to analyze these situations together with the students, draw conclusions, and also teach them to express their thoughts correctly, accurately and consistently. Russian language formation based on the material of scientific texts is therefore a priority area in the university methodology of teaching Russian.

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